

Polarographic Study of Complexes of Cadmium(II) and Lead(II) with Ethoxyacetate Ions

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Reduction of the complexes of cadmium(II) and lead(II) at d.m.e. in aqueous and aqueous-methanol media at $\mu=1.0$ M (NaClO₄) at 15 ± 0.1 and $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ is reversible and diffusion-controlled. Four complex species are formed in either case. The overall stability constants of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 and 1:4 complexes have been determined by DeFord and Hume, and Mihailov's mathematical treatment. Lead(II) complexes have been found to be much stronger than the corresponding cadmium(II) complexes. Thermodynamic parameters have been determined. Percentage distribution of cadmium(II) and lead(II) present in various forms in equilibrium as a function of the ligand concentration have been calculated.

RECENTLY, complexes of certain plant auxins and fungicides with trace elements, cadmium(II), zinc(II), manganese(II) and thallium(I) have been reported^{1,2}. In the present investigation, the interaction of ethoxyacetate, a fungicide, with trace elements cadmium(II) and lead(II) at d.m.e. in aqueous and aqueous-methanol media has been studied. Thermodynamic parameters and percentage distribution of metal ions present in various forms in equilibrium as a function of logarithm of ethoxyacetate concentration have also been calculated.

Experimental

Reagents: Cadmium nitrate tetrahydrate (E.M., A.G.), lead nitrate (B.D.H., AnalaR), sodium perchlorate monohydrate (E.M., G.R.), perchloric acid (Reidel) and Triton-X-100 (Rohm and Haas) were used as such. All the other chemicals used were of guaranteed purity. Triple-distilled mercury and double-distilled water were used in all the manipulations. Methanol was purified and distilled before use³. Ethoxyacetic acid was prepared from sodium ethoxide and freshly distilled chloroacetic acid⁴, and purified by distillation under reduced pressure ($109-111^\circ/17$ mm), b.p. $205-6^\circ$. Structure and purity of the acid was further confirmed by its pmr spectrum.

Solutions: Stock solutions of cadmium(II) and lead(II) were prepared in water and standardised⁵. Sodium salt of ethoxyacetic acid was prepared and

Fig. 1. Plot of $F_j([X])$ functions vs C_x for cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate system in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Fig. 2. Plot of $F_j([X])$ functions vs C_x for cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate system in aqueous medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

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TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF INTERACTION OF CADMIUM(II) AND LEAD(II) WITH ETHOXYACETATE IONS

$Cd^{II}=Pb^{II}=4 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\mu=1 M (NaClO_4)$, $pH=6.8 \pm 0.1$

C_x M	I		II		III		IV		V		VI	
	$E_{1/2}$ $-V$	i_{d_0}/i_{d_c}										
0.00	0.5775	—	0.5865	—	0.5705	—	0.3760	—	0.3810	—	0.3780	—
0.02	0.5800	1.058	0.5885	1.003	0.5750	1.082	0.3875	1.025	0.3845	1.107	0.3850	1.070
0.05	0.5850	1.061	0.5905	1.007	0.5800	1.071	0.3920	1.086	0.3990	1.269	0.3948	1.123
0.10	0.5900	1.107	0.5970	1.029	0.5865	1.122	0.4065	1.112	0.4045	1.286	0.4090	1.181
0.15	0.5945	1.127	0.6000	1.094	0.5913	1.162	0.4125	1.211	0.4145	1.297	0.4110	1.171
0.20	0.5983	1.145	0.6040	1.104	0.5945	1.162	0.4178	1.197	0.4175	1.339	0.4180	1.228
0.25	0.6015	1.149	0.6070	1.108	0.5980	1.260	0.4280	1.200	0.4280	1.285	0.4218	1.242
0.30	0.6048	1.157	0.6095	1.184	0.6020	1.238	0.4270	1.232	0.4260	1.365	0.4265	1.256
0.35	0.6075	1.157	0.6128	1.165	0.6053	1.246	0.4305	1.240	0.4305	1.365	0.4303	1.302
0.40	0.6090	1.263	0.6148	1.220	0.6095	1.234	0.4330	1.365	0.4335	1.445	0.4340	1.314
0.45	0.6115	1.295	0.6170	1.241	0.6115	1.307	0.4363	1.350	0.4370	1.445	0.4375	1.314
0.50	0.6138	1.331	0.6195	1.290	0.6140	1.334	0.4385	1.398	0.4405	1.461	0.4405	1.414
0.60	0.6175	1.346	0.6240	1.297	0.6195	1.411	0.4445	1.399	0.4445	1.515	0.4468	1.390
0.70	0.6220	1.378	0.6270	1.371	0.6235	1.626	0.4490	1.546	0.4485	1.627	0.4508	1.513
0.80	0.6255	1.471	0.6305	1.440	0.6300	1.519	0.4535	1.557	0.4550	1.578	0.4565	1.499
0.90	0.6300	1.471	0.6335	1.412	—	—	0.4580	1.578	0.4580	1.680	—	—

- I Cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- II Cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate in aqueous medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- III Cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate in 10% methanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- IV Lead(II)-ethoxyacetate in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- V Lead(II)-ethoxyacetate in aqueous medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$.
- VI Lead(II)-ethoxyacetate in 10% methanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

pH of this stock solution was adjusted using an Elico pH meter model LI-10. Solutions containing metal ions ($4 \times 10^{-4} M$) and varying concentrations of complexing agent (0-0.9 M) were prepared in

water and 10% methanol media at ionic strength 1 M maintained with sodium perchlorate.

The capillary characteristics measured in 0.1 M sodium perchlorate (open circuit) and at a mercury height of 60 cm were $m=2.012 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$ and $t=3.9 \text{ sec}$. Purified N_2 gas presaturated with the back-

Fig. 3. Plot of $F_j(C_x)$ functions vs C_x for cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate system in 10% methanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Fig. 4. Plot of $F_j(C_x)$ functions vs C_x for lead(II)-ethoxyacetate system in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Fig. 5. Plot of $F_j([X])$ functions vs C_x for lead(II)-ethoxyacetate system in aqueous medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Fig. 6. Plot of $F_j([X])$ functions vs C_x for lead(II)-ethoxyacetate system in 10% methanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

ground solution to be polarographed, was used for deaeration and an inert atmosphere was maintained over the solution during electrolysis. The electrolysis was carried out in a H-cell in conjunction with an agar-agar plug saturated with sodium chloride. Polarograms of 0.4 mM cadmium(II) and lead(II) solutions were obtained in the presence of different concentrations of ethoxyacetate at 15 ± 0.1 and $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using Radelkis model OH-102 polarograph in aqueous and 10% methanol media. Triton-X-100 (0.002% in the final solution) was used as maxima

Fig. 7. Percentage distribution of cadmium in various forms as a function of $-\log C_x$ in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

suppressor whenever required. An iR compensation was used while working with methanolic solutions. The currents were corrected for residual current. The resulting polarographic data as a function of the ligand concentration (C_x), which was calculated from the pH of the solution and pK_a value of the ligand ($pK_a = 3.84 \pm 0.03$), are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Both cadmium(II) and lead(II) give single well-defined reversible polarographic reduction wave. Current is directly proportional to $\sqrt{h_{err}}$, showing that the reduction is diffusion-controlled. Plot of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$ is a straight line with a slope of 31 ± 2 mV. Cathodic reduction of cadmium(II) and lead(II) in ethoxyacetate is, therefore, reversible and involves two electron transfer in either case. That $E_{1/2}$ is independent of h_{err} is in keeping with the reversible character of the wave. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ to more negative potential and decrease in the diffusion current with increase in ethoxyacetate concentration suggest complex formation. The data were analysed for the Fronaeus functions, $F_j([X])$, using DeFord and Hume expression⁷.

The $F_j([X])$ functions thus calculated at different concentrations of the ligand are then solved for the stability constant by a graphical procedure (Figs. 1-6). Plots of $F_0([X])$, $F_1([X])$ and $F_2([X])$ against C_x are smooth curves, while $F_3([X])$ gives a straight line with slope and $F_4([X])$ a straight line parallel to the abscissa confirming the formation of four consecutive complexes, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 in

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF CADMIUM(II) AND LEAD(II) COMPLEXES WITH ETHOXYACETATE IONS

Complex species	Medium	Temp. $\pm 0.1^\circ$	Overall stability constant of			
			Cadmium(II) complex		Lead(II) complex	
			DeFord-Hume method	Mihailov's method	DeFord-Hume method	Mihailov's method
MX ₁	Aqueous	25	16.00	15.91	80.00	66.40
	Aqueous	15	9.00	9.52	60.00	66.97
MX ₂	10% Methanol	25	24.00	24.77	80.00	90.43
	Aqueous	25	34.50	29.86	315.00	217.40
MX ₃	Aqueous	15	36.00	20.69	190.00	192.60
	10% Methanol	25	37.00	58.45	322.00	291.12
MX ₄	Aqueous	25	11.00	36.49	200.00	475.13
	Aqueous	15	15.80	29.98	555.00	369.28
MX ₄	10% Methanol	25	38.00	91.96	750.00	624.79
	Aqueous	25	50.49	33.34	720.91	778.31
	Aqueous	15	25.67	32.57	326.89	581.02
	10% Methanol	25	215.35	108.50	818.44	1005.67

 Fig. 8. Percentage function of cadmium in various forms as a function of $-\log C_x$ in aqueous medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

equilibrium with each other in either case, having stabilities for cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate complexes, $\beta_1 = 16.00$, $\beta_2 = 34.50$, $\beta_3 = 11.00$ and $\beta_4 = 50.49$, and for lead(II)-ethoxyacetate complexes, $\beta_1 = 80.00$, $\beta_2 = 315.00$, $\beta_3 = 200.00$ and $\beta_4 = 720.91$ in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, respectively. The effect of temperature and medium on the stability of the complexes has been studied and the values are $\beta_1 = 9.00$, $\beta_2 = 36.00$, $\beta_3 = 15.80$ and $\beta_4 = 25.67$ in aqueous medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $\beta_1 = 24.00$, $\beta_2 = 37.00$, $\beta_3 = 38.00$ and $\beta_4 = 215.35$ in 10% methanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ for cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate complexes, and $\beta_1 = 60.00$, $\beta_2 = 190.00$, $\beta_3 = 555.00$ and $\beta_4 = 326.39$ in aqueous medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$, and

 Fig. 9. Percentage distribution of cadmium in various forms as a function of $-\log C_x$ in 10% methanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

$\beta_1 = 80.00$, $\beta_2 = 322.00$, $\beta_3 = 750.00$ and $\beta_4 = 813.44$ in 10% methanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, respectively (Table 2).

The complexity function, F_{calc} , at each data point and stability constant of the complexes formed are also determined by Mihailov's method⁸ from the Mihailov's constants 'a' and 'A' and the results are presented in Table 2. There is a reasonably close agreement in the results obtained by the two methods for lead(II)-ethoxyacetate complexes. Although there is a difference between some of the stability constant values determined by the two methods for cadmium(II)-ethoxyacetate complexes, F_{calc} and F_{exp} values show a reasonably close agreement.

The thermodynamic parameters ΔH° , ΔG° and ΔS° are calculated from the effect of temperature

Fig. 10. Percentage distribution of lead in various forms as a function of $-\log C_x$ in aqueous medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Fig. 11. Percentage distribution of lead in various forms as a function of $-\log C_x$ in aqueous medium at $15 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

on the stability constant of the complexes using equations :

$$\Delta H^\circ = -2.303 RT_1 T_2 (\log \beta_{T_1} - \log \beta_{T_2}) / (T_2 - T_1)$$

$$\Delta F^\circ = -2.303 RT (\log \beta)_T$$

$$\Delta F^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T \Delta S^\circ$$

and the results are presented in Table 3. The percentage distribution of the metal ions present in various forms in equilibrium as a function of ethoxyacetate concentration is also calculated and the results are presented graphically in Figs. 7-12.

It is evident from these results that the complexes formed are more stable at lower temperature

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR COMPLEXATION OF CADMIUM(II) AND LEAD(II) WITH ETHOXYACETATE

Complex species	ΔF° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° J deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
CdX ₁	-6.87	+41.06	+160.85
CdX ₂	-8.77	-3.04	+19.25
CdX ₃	-5.94	-25.84	-66.78
CdX ₄	-9.72	+48.28	+194.62
PbX ₁	-10.86	+20.53	+105.34
PbX ₂	-14.26	+36.08	+168.91
PbX ₃	-13.13	-72.84	-200.88
PbX ₄	-16.81	+56.55	+244.50

or in aqueous methanol medium. However, the highest complex in general, becomes less stable on lowering the temperature. Also the complexes of lead(II) with ethoxyacetate are more stable than the corresponding cadmium(II) complexes. Lead(II)-ethoxyacetate complexes are also stronger than those of acetate⁹. Since ethoxyacetate is a considerably weaker base than acetate, the greater stability of the lead(II)-ethoxyacetate complexes may be reasonably ascribed to a certain degree of chelation.

Fig. 12. Percentage distribution of lead in various forms as a function of $-\log C_x$ in 10% methanol medium at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

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